

Synthesis, characterization and X-ray structure of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis(2-benzimidazolymethyl)-1,2-ethanediamine

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Abstract : This work describes the synthesis of octahedral copper(II), [Cu(L)]²⁺ (1) and nickel(II), [Ni(L)]²⁺ (2) complexes of a potentially hexa-coordinating ligand L (L = *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis(2-benzimidazolymethyl)-1,2-ethanediamine), and characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction method. The complex [Cu(L)](ClO₄)₂ crystallizes in the monoclinic system with the space group *C2/c*, *a* = 17.528(4), *b* = 10.895(2) and *c* = 18.986(4) Å, β = 96.54(3)°. The complex [Ni(L)](ClO₄)₂·4H₂O crystallizes in the orthorhombic system with the space group *P2(1)2(1)2(1)*, *a* = 11.952(2), *b* = 15.317(2), *c* = 22.517(5) Å, α = β = γ = 90°. Room temperature magnetic moment studies reveal that both the complexes are paramagnetic with μ_{eff} 2.03 and 2.98 B.M. for copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes respectively. Room temperature EPR studies on polycrystalline powder material of copper(II) complex give <g_{av}> = 2.028 as well as in solution state <g_{av}> = 2.025.

Keywords : Nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes, X-ray crystal structure.

Ethylenediamine tetraacetate (EDTA) is found to be a versatile N/O donor ligand with a strong chelate effect, and forms stable complexes with various types of metal ions. EDTA, although normally a hexadentate ligand can form complexes in which six¹, five^{2,3} or even four^{4,5} of the potential donor atoms in the ligand are attached to the metal center. It can stabilize higher^{1c} as well as normal oxidation states¹⁻⁶ of transition metal ions and is proved to be useful in many analytical applications. A potential hexa-coordinating N₆ donor ligand can be synthesized easily by condensing EDTA with *o*-phenylenediamine in solid state at ~180 °C incorporating benzimidazolyl groups in place of carboxylic acid groups. It is interesting to note, how this ligand behave towards transition metal ions. The coordination chemistry of this ligand and its related analogues is not well studied and there are only few reports on its complexes⁷⁻¹³. This and the related ligands have been found to form dinuclear (μ-oxo) complexes with copper(II)⁷⁻¹¹ and iron(III)^{12,13} having some biological relevance. This work presents the results obtained for the synthesis of mononuclear copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes and their single crystal X-ray structures.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Starting materials for the synthesis of ligand (L) viz. ethylenediamine-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetic acid (Merck, India) and *o*-phenylenediamine (A.R., Loba, India) were of reagent grade and used as received. Solvents like acetone, ethanol, methanol and acetonitrile (Merck, India) were of reagent grade and dried by standard methods before use.

Synthesis of ligand (L) :

Ligand (L) was synthesized by following the general reaction (Scheme 1) in the solid state at 180–190 °C as reported in the literature¹² and characterized by CHN analysis.

Synthesis of [Cu(L)](ClO₄)₂ (1) :

Complex 1 was prepared by adding 0.3182 g Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.86 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) to an ethanolic solution of 0.73 g (0.86 mmol) of L (20 ml) and stirring for about 4 h at room temperature. The solution was then evaporated to dryness and redissolved in hot methanol to afford a dark green solution. It was then

Scheme 1

filtered and kept at room temperature allowing slow evaporation whereupon the dark green crystalline product deposited within 15 days, which was filtered and dried in a desiccator. Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction was obtained by recrystallization from acetonitrile (yield : 75% based on Cu). Composition of the compound was determined by elemental analysis as : C, 48.03; H, 3.93; N, 16.37 and calculated based on $C_{34}H_{32}N_{10}O_8Cl_2Cu$ as : C, 48.42; H, 3.79; N, 16.61. IR (cm^{-1}) 3409, 3057, 2939, 1640, 1466, 1277, 1115, 745, 629. ·

Synthesis of $[Ni(L)](ClO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (2) :

Complex 2 was prepared by adding 0.3139 g $Ni(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.86 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) to an ethanolic solution of 0.73 g (0.86 mmol) of ligand (20 ml) and stirring for about 4 h at room temperature. The solution was then evaporated to dryness and redissolved in hot methanol to provide a dark green solution. It was then filtered and kept at room temperature allowing slow evaporation whereupon the dark violet crystalline product deposited within 5 days. The precipitate was filtered and dried in a desiccator. Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction was obtained by recrystallization from acetonitrile (yield : 65% based on Ni). Composition of the compound was determined by elemental analysis as : C, 45.29; H, 4.49; N, 15.79 and calculated based on $C_{34}H_{40}N_{10}O_{12}Cl_2Ni$ as : C, 44.87; H, 4.39; N, 15.39. IR (cm^{-1}) 3403–3400, 3060, 2939, 1627, 1461, 1275, 1114, 745, 630.

Physical measurements : Elemental analyses were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer 240 elemental analyzer. Infrared spectrum ($400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was recorded from KBr pellets on a Nicolet Magna IR 750 series-II FTIR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded from Agilent 8453-UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were recorded on a PAR vibrating sample magnetometer using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the calibrant. EPR were recorded from Varian model E 112 EPR system.

Crystal data collection and refinement : Intensity data were collected at 293 K for 1 and 2 in the $\theta\text{--}2\theta$ mode using graphite monochromatized $MoK\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073\text{ \AA}$). 3185 unique reflections ($2\theta_{max} = 50^\circ$) were registered for the former complex and 3386 unique re-

flections ($2\theta_{max} = 48^\circ$) for the latter. No decomposition of the crystals occurred during the data collection. The intensities were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects and for absorption using the ψ -scan data. The structures were solved by direct methods with SHELXS-97 and non-hydrogen atoms refined anisotropically by full matrix least-squares on F^2 using SHELXL-97¹⁴. Hydrogen atoms were included in the final refinement stages at their calculated positions (C–H = 0.97 \AA). At convergence $R_1 = 0.048$ [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] and $wR_2 = 0.130$ (all data) for 1 and $R_1 = 0.079$ [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] and $wR_2 = 0.212$ (all data) for 2. Final refinement details are given in Table 1. The maximum peak in the final difference map was 0.67 e \AA^{-3} for 1 and 0.65 e \AA^{-3} for 2.

Results and discussion

Description of the structures :

$[Cu(L)](ClO_4)_2$ (1) : Complex 1 crystallizes in the monoclinic space group $C2/c$. Table 1 summarizes the crystallographic data and refinement parameters, and selected bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 2. The crystallographic numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 1, which was drawn with the ORTEP program using 25% probability ellipsoids.

The coordination about the copper atom is best described by a slightly distorted octahedral geometry in which the copper atom is coordinated by two benzimidazolyl nitrogen and one ethylene diamine nitrogen and their symmetry related counter parts. The bond lengths between central copper and nitrogen atoms are : $Cu(1)\text{--}N(1) = Cu(1)\text{--}N(1\#) = 2.047(3)\text{ \AA}$, and $Cu(1)\text{--}N(2) = Cu(1)\text{--}N(2\#) = 1.991(3)\text{ \AA}$ and $Cu(1)\text{--}N(6) = Cu(1)\text{--}N(6\#) = 2.494(3)\text{ \AA}$. The planer part of the octahedral geometry is coordinated by ethylene diamine nitrogen N(6), benzimidazolyl nitrogen N(1) and their symmetric counterpart, and the axial positions are occupied by benzimidazolyl nitrogen N(2) and its counter part giving a distorted octahedral geometry to the copper atom. The N–Cu–N angles around the copper atom are : $N(1)\text{--}Cu(1)\text{--}N(6) = 74.20(12)^\circ$, $N(6)\text{--}Cu(1)\text{--}N(6\#) = 71.66(11)^\circ$, $N(1\#)\text{--}Cu(1)\text{--}N(6\#) = 74.20(12)^\circ$, $N(1)\text{--}Cu(1)\text{--}N(1\#) = 141.28(14)^\circ$, confirms the equatorial plane.

The metal atom is displaced by 0.015 \AA towards the axial N atom. The axial bond lengths are significantly larger than the equatorial ones and it is due to the Jahn-Teller distortion as well as for the steric crowding of the ligand around copper atom. It is to be noted here that the individual angles in axial as well as equatorial planes

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for complex 1 and complex 2

Parameters	[Cu(C ₃₄ N ₁₀ H ₃₂)](ClO ₄) ₂	[Ni(C ₃₄ N ₁₀ H ₃₂)]·(ClO ₄) ₂ ·4H ₂ O
Empirical formula	C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₁₀ O ₈ Cl ₂ Cu	C ₃₄ H ₄₀ N ₁₀ O ₁₂ Cl ₂ Ni
Formula weight	843.14	910.37
Temperature	293(2) K	293(2) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	0.71073 Å
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, C2/c	Orthorhombic, P2(1)2(1)2(1)
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 17.528(4)$ Å; $\alpha = 90^\circ$ $b = 10.895(2)$ Å; $\beta = 96.54(3)^\circ$ $c = 18.986(4)$ Å; $\gamma = 90^\circ$	$a = 11.952(2)$ Å $b = 15.317(3)$ Å $c = 22.517(5)$ Å
Volume	3602.1(13) Å ³	4122.0(14) Å ³
Z, calculated density	8, 1.555 Mg/m ³	4, 1.467 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.822 mm ⁻¹	0.672 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	1732	1888
Crystal size	0.72 × 0.57 × 0.28 mm	0.64 × 0.52 × 0.43 mm
θ range for data collection	2.16 to 25.05°	
Limiting indices	$0 < h < 20$, $0 < k < 12$, $-22 < l < 22$	$0 < h < 13$, $-17 < k < 0$, $0 < l < 25$
Reflections collected/unique	3295/3185 [R (int) = 0.0762]	3386/3386
Completeness	to $\theta = 22.50(1)$: 99.7%	to $\theta = 27.50(2)$: 93.0%
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical	Semi-empirical
Max. and min. transmission	0.35705 and 0.30970	0.46865 and 0.38034
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	3185/2/255	3386/36/541
Goodness-of-fit- on F^2	1.039	1.040
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0482$, $wR2 = 0.1169$	$R1 = 0.0791$, $wR2 = 0.1896$
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.0688$, $wR2 = 0.1301$	$R1 = 0.1151$, $wR2 = 0.2117$
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.675 and -0.471 e Å ⁻³	0.646 and -0.425 e Å ⁻³

deviate significantly from the ideal values and manifests the distortion of the structure. The intermolecular hydrogen bonds influence the geometry of the molecule in the solid state. Two intermolecular hydrogen bonds, N(11)...O(1) = 2.813(5) Å and N(11)-H(11)...O(1) = 163(3)°; N(21)...O(2) = 2.854(5) Å and N(21)-H(21)...O(2) = 166(3)°, lead to a centro-symmetric "cave" type of architecture. Each perchlorate molecule hydrogen-bonded with two separate Cu-complexes. The perchlorate molecules occupied the caves and bonded symmetry related molecules to form an infinite one-dimensional chain along [1 0 1] direction in which the four perchlorate ions are superbly matched.

[Ni(L)](ClO₄)₂·4H₂O (2) : Complex 2 crystallizes in the orthorhombic space group P2(1)2(1)2(1). Table 1 contains the crystallographic data and refinement parameters and selected bond lengths and bond angles are listed in

Table 2. Fig. 2 shows the ORTEP drawing with atom numbering of the complex 2.

The nickel atom in 2 is coordinated through four benzimidazolyl and two ethylene diamine nitrogen atoms of the ligand giving a slightly distorted octahedral geometry. The Ni-N bond lengths are : Ni(1)-N(1) = 2.054(9) Å, Ni(1)-N(2) = 2.190(10) Å, Ni(1)-N(3) = 2.139(10) Å, Ni(1)-N(4) = 2.094(11) Å, Ni(1)-N(5) = 2.132(9) Å, Ni(1)-N(6) = 2.116(9) Å, which are in the normal range of Ni-N bonds (2.005-2.119) in an octahedral environment of different amine-imine-oxime ligands¹⁵. The two ethylene diamine nitrogen [N(2) and N(3)] and two benzimidazolyl nitrogen [N(5) and N(1)] comprise the square plane whereas the other two benzimidazolyl nitrogen [N(4) and N(6)] occupy the axial positions giving a slightly distorted octahedral geometry to the nickel atom. This is confirmed by 0.017 Å displacement of Ni atom

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of Cu-complex (1) with 25% probability ellipsoids

from the plane towards one axial N atom. N–Ni–N angles around the nickel atom which are : N(1)–Ni–N(2) = 79.1(4)°, N(1)–Ni–N(5) = 119.5(4)°, N(5)–Ni–N(3) = 77.8(4)°, N(3)–Ni–N(2) = 84.6(4)°. Complex 2 contains four water molecules of crystallization one of which exhibits a four-fold disorder.

Crystal packing of Ni-complex are formed by three types of hydrogen bonding which are : N(7)...O(1) = 2.997(16) Å and N(7)–H(7)...O(1) = 121(11)°; N(8)...OW(2) = 2.833(18) Å and N(8)–H(8)...OW(2) = 171(15)°; N(10)...OW(3) = 3.12(2)Å and N(10)–

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram of Ni-complex (2) with 25% probability ellipsoids

H(10)...OW(3) = 165(13)°. In this crystal packing each Ni-complex exists in discrete form and also in this crystal packing there are some disordered water molecules and perchlorate molecules.

IR spectra : The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})_{\text{aromatic}}$ found at 1600 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is blue shifted by 26 and 39 cm^{-1} in the complexes 1 and 2 respectively suggesting the involvement of the double bonded nitrogen of imidazole ring.

The IR band corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})_{\text{aliphatic}}$ of free ligand slightly change in its position in the complex (1) while it is shifted by 32 cm^{-1} in complex 2 indicating the involvement of the aliphatic amine nitrogens in bonding

Table 2. Selected bond lengths [Å] and angles [°] for 1 and 2

1			
Cu(1)–N(1)#1	2.047(3)	N(1)–Cu(1)–N(#1)	141.28(14)
Cu(1)–N(2)#2	1.991(3)	N(2)–Cu(1)–N(#2)	166.35(14)
Cu(1)–N(6)#6	2.494(3)	N(6)–Cu(1)–N(#6)	71.66(11)
N(1)–Cu(1)–N(6)	74.20(12)	N(#1)–Cu(1)–N(6)	74.20(12)
2			
Ni(1)–N(1)	2.054(9)	N(4)–Ni(1)–N(6)	171.8(4)
Ni(1)–N(4)	2.094(11)	N(1)–Ni(1)–N(5)	119.5(4)
Ni(1)–N(6)	2.116(10)	N(5)–Ni(1)–N(3)	77.8(4)
Ni(1)–N(5)	2.132(9)	N(1)–Ni(1)–N(2)	79.1(4)
Ni(1)–N(3)	2.139(10)	N(3)–Ni(1)–N(2)	84.6(4)
Ni(1)–N(2)	2.190(10)		

in complexes **1** and **2**. The appearance of an IR band at 628 and 630 nm in **1** and **2** respectively which is absent in the free ligand, indicates the presence of perchlorate ions in the complexes. The presence of IR band at 3400 indicates the presence of water molecule in complex **2**.

Electronic spectra : While electronic spectroscopy is at best a modest guide to structure, Hathaway¹⁶ has found a correlation between the energies of the d-d transitions of CuN_x ($x = 4-6$) species and their structure. Complexes with tetragonal-octahedral CuN_6 chromophores have transitions in the region 15500–18500 cm^{-1} , and those with square planar CuN_4 chromophores have transitions in the region 18000–20000 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectrum runs in acetonitrile solution for complex **1** shows an absorption band at 680 nm (14700 cm^{-1}) with $\epsilon = 128 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be attributed to the ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition and is compatible with the complex having an octahedral geometry¹⁷⁻¹⁹. A second band at 320 nm (31250 cm^{-1}) with $\epsilon = 873 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to an LMCT transition in an octahedral geometry. The complex **2** has broad bands at ~ 970 nm (8000–10000 cm^{-1}), $\epsilon = 15 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 560 nm (17850 cm^{-1}), $\epsilon = 20 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and correspond to the electronic transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) respectively. Absorption band at ~ 355 nm (28170 cm^{-1}), $\epsilon = 40 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to as ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3) transition.

Magnetic moment studies : The magnetic moments for the two complexes $[\text{M}^{\text{II}}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ni}$ and Cu) have been measured at room temperature using a vibration sample magnetometer. The μ_{eff} values evaluated to be 2.03 and 2.98 B.M. for copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes respectively.

EPR studies : Room temperature solid-state EPR spectrum of the polycrystalline complex **1** shows typical rhombic spectra with four component anisotropic g -factor. This is an well resolved four line spectrum, typical for copper(II) ion ($I = 3/2$). Generally, copper(II) ion in mononuclear complexes in solid state are not so well resolved, as it is found in the present case. The reason for this kind of observation may be due to the fact that the central ion is well buried inside a non-polar bulky organic ligand, which separates it from the surrounding metal center, i.e. magnetically dilute. This is generally achieved by doping a magnetic center into a diamagnetic host. The three g values calculated to be : $g_1 = 2.0497$, $g_2 = 2.02503$ and $g_3 = 2.0097$ with $\langle g_{\text{av}} \rangle = 2.028$.

EPR spectrum in acetonitrile solution of $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) is nearly the

same as in solid with poor resolution of the peaks. The three g values are calculated to be : $g_1 = 2.03804$, $g_2 = 2.02158$ and $g_3 = 2.01502$ with $\langle g_{\text{av}} \rangle = 2.025$. It indicates that the local symmetry of this complex in solid as well-in solution remains virtually the same.

Supplementary materials :

The crystallographic data for **1** and **2** have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre with CCDC nos. 213080 and CCDC nos. 213081 respectively. Copies are available free of charge on application to the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : int. Code +44(0)1223/336-033, E-mail : deposit@chemcrs.carn.ac.uk).

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